

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Argentina

Version 1.0

**International
Science Council**

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About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the World Data System (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

<https://www.worlddatasystem.org/>

About the WDS series on Scientific Data Repository-related Policies:

The World Data System (WDS) [Policy Series](#) reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

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Acronyms

SNRD	National System of Data Repositories
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative – Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

Introduction

Established in 2013, National Law N.º 26.899 mandates that scientific institutions in Argentina create and maintain open access digital repositories. This legislation aims to enhance the accessibility and reusability of research data and publications, fostering collaboration among researchers and facilitating public access to scientific knowledge.

The primary objective of the National Law N.º 26.899 is to ensure that the results of scientific research are readily accessible to the public. By requiring institutions to deposit research data and publications within a maximum period of five years, the law promotes transparency and the dissemination of knowledge. This approach not only benefits researchers by enabling them to build upon existing work but also ensures that the general public can access scientific advancements.

To comply with the National Law N.º 26.899, scientific institutions must establish digital repositories that are open to the public. These repositories should be designed to store and manage primary research data and scientific publications efficiently. Institutions are responsible for ensuring that their repositories meet the standards set forth by the law, including timely access to research data.

The implementation of open access repositories has a significant impact on both the research community and the general public. For researchers, these repositories provide a platform for sharing their work, facilitating collaboration, and increasing the visibility of their research. For the public, open access to scientific information enhances education and awareness, allowing individuals to stay informed about scientific developments.

Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies

Scientific data repository related policies specific to Argentina include:

- [National Law No. 26.899 on Institutional Digital Repositories of Open Access \(2013\)](#)

This law establishes that publicly funded scientific institutions must create and maintain open access digital repositories. It requires that primary research data and scientific publications be deposited in these repositories within a maximum period of five years from their collection, promoting the accessibility and reproducibility of scientific work for reuse by other researchers and the general public.

- [Open Data Plan - Decree 117/2016 \(2016\)](#)

This decree guarantees public access to information generated and managed by state agencies. Therefore, it urges ministries, secretariats, and decentralized and deconcentrated agencies under the National Executive Power to carry out an "Open Data Plan." It must detail the data assets under their jurisdiction and/or supervision and have an established publication schedule for the data.

- [National System of Data Repositories](#)

The SNRD is a system that integrates various digital repositories in Argentina, promoting access to scientific and technical information. This system aims to integrate and coordinate the different existing digital repositories in the country, facilitating access to scientific information.

The SNRD Guidelines, published in 2015, establish standards to ensure the interoperability of national and international scientific repositories. They are based on standards such as [Dublin Core](#) and protocols like [OAI-PMH](#), and specify mandatory metadata (title, author, subject, description, etc.) and open access formats. These guidelines promote access, preservation, and sustainability of national scientific production. This aligns Argentine repositories with global networks.

- [Resolution E-753/2016 of the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Productive Innovation of Argentina](#)

This resolution regulates National Law No. 26.899 on Institutional Digital Repositories of Open Access enacted in 2013. The resolution defines several key aspects: it indicates that all research personnel of state-funded institutions must deposit a copy of their scientific and academic publications, including articles, theses, and research data, in the institutional repository. Researchers have a period of six months from the publication of their work to make the deposit in the corresponding repository. It also states that materials in the repositories must be open access, although there are exceptions, such as in cases of intellectual property or if the data affects confidentiality or national security. The resolution also indicates that repositories must comply with technical interoperability standards, allowing them to be integrated into national and international networks for access to scientific information. Finally, it establishes that institutions have the responsibility to ensure the implementation of the repositories and ensure that personnel comply with the law.

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